

Anion Exchange Distribution Studies of Some Metal Ions in Aqueous Nitrite and Aqueous Methanol-Nitrite Media

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Anion exchange equilibrium distribution of fifteen metal ions have been studied in aqueous nitrite and aqueous methanol nitrite media using Dowex-21K in nitrate form. The ions such as Hg(II), Cd(II) and Ag(I), which were expected to form stable metal nitrite complexes gave high K_D values. Studies in aqueous nitrite media suggested the following selectivity sequence of common transition and post transition ions for the anion exchanger used.

Out of the less common metal ions studied uranyl (II) and Ce(III) gave quite high distribution values. Separation possibilities for many metal ions by ion exclusion technique have been suggested.

Use of methanol as a water miscible less polar solvent mixed with water increased the K_D values with increasing methanol percentage in the solution generally suggesting stabilization of metal nitrite complexes in such solutions. Utility of such solvents has also been shown for planning certain useful separations.

A variety of complexing media have been used to study the metal ion exchange on anion exchangers and their uses has been done in many analytical separations. Amongst them the mineral acids and their salts form a class of complexing agents which has been used by many workers. Thus the use of hydrochloric acid media has been done by Kraus and Nelson¹ and Bunney *et al.*²; while mixed hydrochloric acid-hydrofluoric acid media was used by Nelson *et al.*³. Pure hydrofluoric acid media was used by Faris (4) to provide elution characteristics of some 50 elements, Kraus and Nelson^{1,3,5} have reported metal ion distribution data in pure nitric acid also. Similarly the sulphate² and phosphate media have also been used.

As the presence of water miscible polar organic solvents proved advantageous in the metal ion exchange in complexing media. The use of mineral acids and their salts has been done in a variety of non-aqueous and mixed aqueous solvents. Some recent reviews by Korkish⁷, Marcus⁸ and Strelow⁹ summarise their attempts in quite a detailed manner.

A new nitrite media was used by Bhatnagar *et al.*¹⁰ for studying the distribution of some metal ion in aqueous and mixed ethanol media. In this communication anion exchange distribution studies with 15 metal ions using sodium nitrite in aqueous and aqueous methanolic solutions have been reported. The data has been procured on a new commercially available exchanger-Dowex-21K in nitrate form.

Experimental

Exchange Resin :

An anion exchange resin, Dowex-21K in nitrate form was used for all anion exchange distribution studies. It was a strong base anion exchanger of analytical grade (50-100 mesh). The air dried resin ($\sim 25^\circ$) had a capacity of 3.6 meq./gm. and a moisture contents of $\sim 20\%$.

Metal ion Solutions

All metal salt solutions were prepared from their nitrates (AR reagents of British Drug House) to give 0.2 N stock solutions in aqueous medium. Thus solutions of Ag(I), Tl(I), Pb(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Ce(III) and U(VI) were prepared directly in double distilled water. Minimum quantity of pure nitric acid was added to the stock solutions of Hg(II), ($\sim 0.2\%$) and Zr(IV) ($\sim 1\%$) to check their hydrolysis. Bismuth(III) solution was prepared in presence of mannitol as detailed in an earlier communication¹¹.

The stock solutions were suitably diluted with double distilled water or with methanol (AR, BDH) and water to give metal ion solution of 0.05 N concentration in purely aqueous or aqueous methanolic (20, 40, 60% v/v) solutions.

Determination of Various Elements

Most of these elements as cobalt(II), nickel(II), cadmium(II), zinc(II), lead(II), bismuth(III), zirconium(IV),

nium(IV) and thorium(IV) were estimated titrimetrically with disodium EDTA using appropriate metal indicator. Silver(I) and mercury(II) were determined with ammonium thiocyanate in nitric acid medium using ferric ion as indicator. Thallium(I) was estimated with potassium iodate. Estimation of copper was done iodometrically. Iron(III) was estimated by permanganate while Ce(II) was titrated with Mohr's salt solution. Only uranium(VI) was estimated gravimetrically as oxinate. For metal ion estimation in distribution studies in nitrite media destruction of nitrite ion was a pre-requisite.

Determination of Distribution Coefficient

All distribution studied were performed in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks (250 ml.) with exactly 1 gm. of the resin and 50 ml. of the solution containing the same quantity of metal ion (0.05 N) in aqueous and different methanolic nitrite media. Batches were equilibrated by shaking for 24 hours. Each solution was then analysed for the metal ion.

The weight distribution coefficients (K_D) were calculated from the relation.

$$K_D = \frac{\text{meq metal per 1 gm. of dry resin}}{\text{meq. metal per 1 ml. of solution}}$$

The results have been tabulated in Table 1-4 for aqueous and 20, 40 and 60% (v/v) aqueous methanolic solutions.

TABLE 1—ANION EXCHANGE DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN AQUEOUS NITRITE MEDIA ON DOWEX-21K (NO_2^-)

Ions	Nitrite concentrations, N						
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5	2.0
Ag(I)	7	50	44	19	35	30	42
Tl(I)	0	0	1	2	0	4	4
Hg(II)	ppt	ppt	283	271	173	248	205
Pb(II)	6	17	19	19	19	19	15
Cu(II)	0	2	10	14	26	31	34
Zn(II)	2	4	7	10	17	22	29
Cd(II)	0	27	59	64	89	89	33
Co(II)	1	2	5	10	11	11	18
Ni(II)	3	3	4	2	1	3	5
Fe(III)	6	3	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Bi(III)	5	23	25	39	—	63	63
Ce(III)	61	122	135	135	167	167	13
$\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$	61	89	61	128	172	ppt	ppt
Zr(IV)	13	6	4	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Th(IV)	44	54	19	18	24	41	44

TABLE 2—ANION EXCHANGE DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN 20% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL SOLUTIONS

Ions	Nitrite concentrations, N						
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5	2.0
Ag(I)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Tl(I)	1	6	11	26	8	27	106
Hg(II)	ppt	ppt	251	172	169	271	205
Pb(II)	12	28	32	32	28	23	21
Cu(II)	5	26	28	39	70	84	58
Zn(II)	3	10	12	19	25	28	38
Cd(II)	14	75	78	89	38	19	38
Co(II)	1	5	8	37	40	44	59
Ni(II)	3	5	6	1	5	5	14
Fe(III)	2	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Bi(III)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ce(III)	167	166	134	234	396	ppt	ppt
$\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$	137	102	108	54	ppt	ppt	ppt
Zr(IV)	19	142	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Th(IV)	24	25	13	13	27	93	111

TABLE 3—ANION EXCHANGE DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN 40% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL SOLUTIONS

Ions	Nitrate concentrations, N						
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5	2.0
Ag(I)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Tl(I)	0	6	0	0	2	3	5
Hg(II)	ppt	ppt	163	117	162	205	140
Pb(II)	24	32	32	32	25	19	16
Cu(II)	ppt	ppt	ppt	55	131	133	92
Zn(II)	5	19	27	38	38	48	52
Cd(II)	5	65	105	7	122	24	15
Co(II)	6	11	26	26	37	37	82
Ni(II)	5	8	3	5	6	14	27
Fe(III)	3	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Bi(III)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ce(III)	62	102	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
$\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$	55	36	23	32	ppt	ppt	ppt
Zr(IV)	33	1	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Th(IV)	23	10	6	12	8	23	23

TABLE 4—ANION EXCHANGE DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN 60% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL SOLUTIONS

Ions	Nitrite concentrations, N						
	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5	2.0
Ag(I)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Tl(I)	0	0	0	0	0	3	3
Hg(II)	ppt	ppt	137	169	140	162	119
Pb(II)	38	56	54	46	39	32	27
Cu(II)	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	235	254	95
Zn(II)	4	21	38	44	44	52	52
Cd(II)	6	111	97	46	27	20	65
Co(II)	6	41	59	66	47	47	47
Ni(II)	8	9	17	21	31	41	52
Fe(III)	3	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Bi(III)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ce(III)	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
UO ₂ (II)	73	60	28	44	ppt	ppt	ppt
Zr(IV)	158	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt	ppt
Th(IV)	12	2	0	0	0	9	27

During the preparation of the solution phase insoluble compounds were formed in some cases. Such cases have been indicated by ppt in the tables. No distribution studies could be done in such cases.

Results and Discussion

The study of usual type of ion-exchange equilibria is useful in predicting the selectivity trends for ions of different types under the experimental conditions. But when a complexing agent is present in the solution phase, the exchange equilibria is modified according to the nature of the complexed species in the solution. Thus in such cases two equilibria are at work in the solution phase – (1) ion exchange equilibria and (2) the complex equilibria. The nature of the complexed ion formed due to the complex equilibria decides the fate of the sorbable ion on an exchanger.

If the complexing ligand is a negative ion, it may lead to stepwise formation of complexes of various types differing in the overall change of the species. Nitrite ion is such an ion which can form several ionic species in solution with metal ions, finally giving stable negatively charged complexed ions. If such a system is brought in contact with an anion exchanger, we can expect more and more metal ion uptake (as a negatively charged complexed ion) with increasing concentration of the negatively charged ligand. This is so when the metal-nitrite complex is a stable negatively charged species. Formation of less stable complexes or no

complex formation at all may lead to lesser or no exchange on an anion exchanger. Hence measured K_D values may be regarded as a rough measure of the stabilities of the complexes.

The results of Table 1 can now be considered to see the effect of the added sodium nitrite to the metal ion uptake by an anion distribution exchanger. Practically in all the cases the metal ion distribution coefficients have shown an increase upto a certain nitrite concentration. But the maximum K_D values were obtained at different nitrite concentration in different cases.

Mercury(II) gave maximum K_D at 0.5 N nitrite concentration, while silver(I) could give it between 0.3–0.5 N. Cadmium(II) gave a maximum at 1.0–1.5 N nitrite concentration. Similarly both Ce(III) and uranyl ions gave maximum K_D values at ~1.0 N nitrite concentration. All these ions have been considered to be forming quite stable nitrite complexes. Very high values of K_D for Hg(II) are indicative of this fact. Though these values decreased a bit by increasing nitrite concentration from 0.5 to 0.7, 1.0 or 1.5 M, but still they were highest of all ions studied. Thus Hg(II) nitrite complexes were the most preferred complexed species for Dowex-21K.

Out of the other common transition and post transition metal ions Cd(II) and Ag(I) were much preferred by this resin as compared to ions as Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pb(II). From the K_D data of metal ions in Table I can be given the following selectivity sequence for the anion exchanger studied.

The higher K_D value of 62 for Bi(III) which does not give nitrite complex can be due to considerable electrolytic sorption in presence of this salt (or may it be mannitol). Similarly zero or negligibly small values of K_D for Tl(I) are also due to the fact that it does not form nitrite complexes^{1,11,12}.

It is thus clear from Table 1 that Hg(II) can be separated from Tl(I), Pb(II) and Bi(III) at any nitrite concentration above 0.5 N. Very good ion exclusion separations can be carried out for these later metal ions from Hg(II) in nitrite media. Results also show possibilities of Cd(II) separations from Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) at about 1.0 N nitrite concentration.

Amongst the less familiar ions such as UO₂(II), Ce(III), Th(IV) and Zr(IV) the separation of Ce(III) from Th and Zr can be planned at about 0.5 N nitrite concentration. Uranyl ion can be conveniently separated from Th(IV) at any nitrite concentration from 0.7–1.0 N. The anion exchange sequence for these ions in nitrite media may be written as :

Considering now the results of metal ion distribution in aqueous methanolic solutions (Table 2 to 4) it can be said that generally for transition metal ions the distribution of the metal ion on an anion exchanger increased with increasing methanol concentration. It was true for all these cases where no precipitation was seen in mixed solvent systems. But for Hg(II) the trend was opposite.

It has been shown by several authors¹³⁻¹⁷ that the presence of a less polar solvent mixed with water, enhances the extent of complex formation. This is why the distribution coefficients of Pb(II), Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cd(II) showed an increase in solvents with higher methanol concentration. The peculiar trend in Hg(II) might be due to increased ion pair formation in solvents of lower dielectric constants (i.e. with 40 or 60% methanol).

The use of water miscible organic solvents thus definitely modifies distribution tendencies of different ions on an anion exchanger. Hence such systems can provide better K_D values for certain pairs of ions to get separated. Thus separation of Cd(II) from Zn(II) Ni(II) can be anticipated in 60% methanol at 0.3 N nitrite concentration. At a higher nitrite concentration (1.5N) Cu(II) - Cd(II) separation possibilities can also be predicted. Of course the use of such mixed solvents did not prove useful for ions such as Ag(I), Bi(III), Fe(III), Zr(IV), Ce(III), UO₂(II) etc. as they gave precipitation on adding nitrite to mixed solvents apparently due to insolubility of electrolytes used.

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